

Creative Commons License Use Survey for Language-related Digital Creations

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Introduction

This survey instrument is designed to understand how creators use (or decide not to use) Creative Commons licenses. The target survey participants are people who create materials for documentation, maintenance, instruction, learning, and/or revitalization of Indigenous, minority, endangered, and/or low-resourced languages. Many people who do work in this area put Creative Commons licenses on their works and share them via, for example, the Wikimedia ecosystem, audio/video sharing platforms, and/or language archives. Part 1 of this survey is designed to learn about the digital creation formats and sharing practices in this specific community of practice. Parts 2 through 4 of this survey contain general questions intended to elicit information about research participants’

- knowledge and awareness of Creative Commons (CC) licenses;
- understanding of how to apply CC licenses to their digital creations;
- interest in and experience with applying CC licenses to their digital creations;
- motivations for and barriers to applying CC licenses to their digital creations; and
- understanding of how to adapt or reuse digital creations licensed with CC licenses.

This survey can be easily adapted for use in other communities of practice by editing some of the questions and multiple-choice responses.

Ethics

Users of this survey should ensure that they comply with all ethics requirements for research studies with human subjects (e.g., Internal Review Board, Ethics Review Board) that might be relevant to and/or required by their specific situation (e.g., community or tribal government, university or institution, or other governing body). This survey includes an example consent form; however, survey users should modify this consent form or create a new one according to their specific ethics requirements.

Survey Software

This survey instrument was created using Qualtrics software.

Link to the survey: https://utexas.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_0DhDEj8cVdaJ7pk.

A copy of the Qualtrics Survey File (Creative_Commons_License_Use_Survey.qsf) can be downloaded [here](#). This file can be used to recreate this survey in your own instance of the Qualtrics software. A PDF of the questions that includes the graphics used in the survey questions is [here](#). Note that the graphics do not appear in the survey questions below in this document.

Translations

I welcome collaborative translations of this survey, especially into Spanish and/or Portuguese. If you are interested in translating this survey, please let me know (skung@utexas.edu).

Translations of questions can be easily added to the Qualtrics software to produce a complete translation of the interactive survey.

The Survey

The survey is divided into six blocks in the Qualtrics software:

1. Introduction-Consent (1 question)
2. Part 1: Your Digital Creations (2 questions)
3. Part 2: Applying Creative Commons Licenses (21 questions)
4. Part 3: Motivations & Barriers (7 questions)
5. Part 4: Reusing CC-licensed Creations (9 questions)
6. Conclusion (0 questions)

Each of these blocks begins with a text-only explanation before the actual questions begin; the conclusion contains only summary text and no questions. Aside from the consent question, the survey questions are organized into four blocks labeled as *parts*. Each question and part-text-screen has a Qualtrics number that begins with the letter Q followed by a sequential number. Below these numbers are indicated in parentheses. The text-screens for the Introduction, Consent, and Conclusion have these labels instead of numbers. The way I have set up the survey in Qualtrics, all multiple-choice questions require a response. Open-ended questions do not require a response, but the respondent will be prompted to answer the question before progressing to the next block; below these questions are indicated by an asterisk after the number, as in (Q31*). If a multiple-choice question allows more than one answer, this is indicated by (*select all that apply*) after the question.

Survey Introduction-Consent

Creative Commons License Use Survey for Language-Related Digital Creations

This survey is designed to understand how creators use (or decide not to use) Creative Commons licenses. The target survey participants are people who create materials for documentation, maintenance, instruction, learning, and/or revitalization of Indigenous, minority, and/or low-resourced languages.

Part 1 of this survey is designed to learn about the digital creation formats and sharing practices in this specific community of practice. Parts 2 through 4 of this survey contain general questions intended to elicit information about research participants'

- knowledge and awareness of Creative Commons (CC) licenses.
- understanding of how to apply CC licenses to their digital creations.
- interest in and experience with applying CC licenses to their digital creations.
- motivations for and barriers to applying CC licenses to their digital creations.
- understanding of how to adapt or reuse digital creations licensed with CC licenses.

This survey begins with a consent form.

Informed Consent

Creative Commons License Use on Language-related Digital Creations: Informed Consent Document

This document has information to help you decide whether or not you wish to participate in this research project. Your participation in this project is completely voluntary. Please discuss any questions you have about the study or about this form with the project staff before deciding to participate.

Introduction

You are invited to participate in a research study to explore:

- creators' knowledge and awareness of Creative Commons (CC) licenses;
- creators' understanding of how to apply a CC licenses to their digital creations;
- creators' interest in and experience with applying CC licenses to their digital creations;
- creators' motivations for and barriers to applying CC licenses to their digital creations;
- creators' understanding of how to adapt/reuse digital creations licensed with CC licenses.

You are being invited to participate in this study because you are a creator of digital materials meant to be used for documentation, maintenance, instruction, learning, and/or revitalization of an Indigenous, minority, and/or low-resourced language [**or insert specific parameters for participant inclusion**].

Description of Procedures

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to complete an online survey. The survey will contain both open-ended and closed-ended questions on the following topics:

- Creative Commons (CC) licenses
- Applying CC licenses to digital media creations
- Reusing digital media licensed with CC licenses
- Incentive for and barriers to using CC licenses

Your participation in this survey will last for approximately 15 minutes [**insert length of time depending on the number of questions your survey contains**]. The researcher will complete data analysis through Qualtrics [**insert data analysis measures to be taken**]. Survey responses are completely anonymous, and all responses will be aggregated into quantitative data. Responses to open-ended questions will be compiled.

Risks or Discomforts

There are no known risks or discomforts expected to result from this study.

Benefits

It is hoped that the information gained in this study will benefit society by describing how a particular community of content creators use open licenses to share their creations.

Costs and Compensation

You will not be paid or otherwise compensated for your participation in this survey. [**Indicate if there will be any monetary costs or compensation for completing the survey.**]

Participant Rights

Participating in this study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to take part in the study or to stop participating at any time, for any reason, without penalty or negative consequences.

Confidentiality

To ensure confidentiality to the extent permitted by law, the following measures will be taken:

- No identifying information will be collected as part of this survey.
- No demographic information will be collected as part of this survey.
- All survey responses are anonymous and confidential.
- All survey responses will be aggregated and considered together.

[Describe the measures you will take to ensure the confidentiality of your participants' data.]

Questions

If you have questions at any time during this study, you are encouraged to contact **[insert the name and contact information of the study's Principal Investigator]**.

Consent and Authorization Provisions

By clicking through to participate in the survey below, you are indicating that you voluntarily agree to participate in this study, that the study has been explained to you, that you have been given the time to read the document, and that your questions have been satisfactorily answered. Please print a copy of this form for your records.

Do you consent to participate in this survey?

- Yes
- No (Selecting this option will immediately end the survey)

(Q1) Part 1: Your Digital Creations

This section contains questions about the kinds of digital materials that you create for the purpose of activities associated with **documentation, maintenance, instruction, learning, and/or revitalization of Indigenous, minority, and/or low-resourced languages** and how you share these materials or make them available to others.

“Digital materials” refers to any digital media files in any format that you consider to be the result of or useful for language documentation, maintenance, instruction, learning, and/or revitalization efforts. From this point on, these materials will be referred to as your **language-related digital creations** or simply your **creations**.

For the purposes of this survey, it does not matter if you are the sole creator of these creations, or if you were a co-creator, i.e., a member of a team of people who collaborated to create the creations. Please consider all of these to be your creations.

(Q2) What digital formats do you create? (Select all that apply)

- audio/video
- audio only (no video)
- video only (no audio)
- photographs
- maps
- digital art (drawing, sketches, animations, cartoons, other graphics, infographics, etc.)
- text-based files (dictionaries, articles, essays, blog posts, books, databases, etc.)

- open educational resources (OER)
- apps (interactive applications or programs)
- other (please specify) [text box]

(Q3) Which of these digital platforms have you used to share your creations with other people (team members, classmates, collaborators, the general public on that platform, anyone at all)? (Select all that apply)

- Digital repository or language archive (e.g., AILLA, ELAR, GitHub, TROLLing, Zenodo, FigShare, Mukurtu, university-based data or institutional repository, a tribal or community-based digital repository)
- Video-sharing platforms (YouTube, Vimeo, etc.)
- Audio-sharing platforms (SoundCloud, Spotify, Apple Podcasts, Google Podcasts, etc.)
- Social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Reddit, TikTok, etc.)
- Photo-sharing platforms (Flickr, Google Photos, etc.)
- Wikimedia Foundation platforms (Wikimedia Commons, Wikibooks, Wiktionary, Wikiversity, Wikidata)
- Cloud-based storage (GoogleDrive, DropBox, OneDrive, etc.)
- Instant messaging platforms (WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Skype, Slack, etc.)
- Website or blog (personal, community, school)
- Writing/blogging platform (Medium, Patreon, Ghost, Write.as, etc.)
- Traditional publishing, non-open access (books, journals, magazines)
- Open access publishing (books, journals, magazines)
- Open Educational Resources (OER), via OER publishers, websites, learning management systems
- Email
- I have never shared a language-related digital creation
- Other (please specify) [text box]

(Q4) Part 2: Applying Creative Commons Licenses

This section asks questions about your use of Creative Commons licenses on your own language-related digital creations. Please read the following definitions before answering the questions in this section. These definitions are available [here](#) (link opens in a new tab) for easier access as you answer the questions in this section.

- *Copyright*: a set of several rights that automatically apply to a creative work at the moment it is created. These rights belong exclusively to the creator of the work for the duration of their life, and to their heir(s) for a set number of years (50 to 100, depending on the jurisdiction) after the creator's death. Thereafter, the work passes into the public domain.
- *Public Domain*: a body of expressed knowledge, ideas, and creativity to which copyright does not apply. Anyone in the world may use works in the public domain free of charge and for any purpose; thus, under the Western belief system, the public domain benefits everyone.

- *Open licenses*: open licenses, like the Creative Commons licenses, work in conjunction with copyright and can be applied to a creation that is protected by copyright. They help ensure that creations will not be locked into copyright's “all rights reserved” model for 50 to 100 years past the lifetime of the creators, and that other people will be able share, copy, and adapt these works, according to the terms of the open license.
- *Licensor*: the person who owns the copyrights to a creation and allows, by means of a license, someone else to use some of those copyrights.
- *Licensee*: the person to whom the license is granted; also, the person who is given permission, by means of a license, to copy, share, or adapt a copyrighted creation.
- *Adaptation, remix, derivative work*: a creation that is based on another work or on multiple other works. In the Creative Commons ecosystem, the terms *adaptation*, *remix*, and *derivative work* are used interchangeably.

(Q5) Have you previously heard of Creative Commons licenses?

- yes
- not sure
- no

(Q6) Have you previously heard of the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication Tool? This also called CC0 or CC-Zero. When you apply CC-Zero to your creation, you give up all of your copyrights and dedicate your creation to the public domain.

- yes
- not sure
- no

(Q7) Have you ever seen any of these logos, licenses, or tools? (Select all that apply)

- CC logo
- 6 CC license buttons
- CC0 button
- I have never seen any of these.

(Q8) Have you ever received or taken any of the following kinds of training about how to use Creative Commons licenses? (Select all that apply)

- I have never received or taken any training on how to use Creative Commons licenses.
- I completed the Creative Commons Certificate Course.
- I attended a training/workshop (live or online) offered by a library, archive, museum, school, or other organization.
- I read about CCLs on the Creative Commons website.
- I read about CCLs on Wikipedia.
- Other (please specify) [text box]

(Q9) How confident do you feel in your understanding of what the CC licenses mean when you see them on digital media?

- Very confident
- Somewhat confident

- Neutral
- Somewhat unconfident
- Not at all confident

(Q10) Have you ever been required to apply a CC license to your own creation? (e.g., publishing in an open access journal; contributing to the Wikimedia ecosystem; following a policy of your university or funder; following instructions for a class or course assignment; etc.)

- yes, next Q
- maybe, next Q
- no, skip to Q14

(Q11) What person or organization required you to put a CC license on your creation? (Select all that apply)

- A teacher, professor, or workshop facilitator
- An Elder
- A boss or supervisor
- Open access journal or publisher
- Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons, or other Wikimedia platform
- My school or university
- My grant/scholarship/fellowship funder
- I can't remember
- Other (please specify) [text box]

(Q12) What formats did you apply a CCL to? (Select all that apply)

- Repeat same list as Q2
- I can't remember
- other (please specify) [text box]

(Q13) Which CC license did you (or a third party) apply to your creation? (Select all that apply)

- 6 CC license buttons
- CC0 button
- I can't remember

(Q14) Have you ever voluntarily applied a CC license to your own creation (i.e., you were not required to do so)?

- yes, next Q
- maybe, next Q
- no, skip to Q17

(Q15) What formats did you apply a CCL to? (Select all that apply) [ats did you apply a CCL to? (Select all that apply)]

- Repeat same list as Q2
- I can't remember

(Q16) Which CCL did you apply to your creation? (Select all that apply)

- 6 CC license buttons
- CC0 button
- I can't remember

(Q17) Have you ever used, or would you ever use, a CC license with the ND (No Derivatives) element? (CC BY-ND or CC BY-NC-ND)

- Definitely yes
- Probably yes
- Neutral
- Probably not
- Definitely not

(Q18*) Why or why not?

- [text box]

(Q19) Have you ever used, or would you ever use, a CC license with the NC (Non-Commercial) element? (CC BY-NC or CC BY-NC-ND or CC BY-NC-SA)

- Definitely yes
- Probably yes
- Neutral
- Probably not
- Definitely not

(Q20*) Why or why not?

- [text box]

(Q21) Have you ever used, or would you ever use, a CC license with the SA (Share-Alike) element?

- Definitely yes
- Probably yes
- Neutral
- Probably not
- Definitely not

(Q22*) Why or why not?

- [text box]

(A23) To what percentage of your creations do you apply CC licenses?

- [slider] 0 to 100%

(A24) How confident do you feel in your understanding of how to apply CC licenses to your creations?

- Very confident
- Somewhat confident
- Neutral

- Somewhat unconfident
- Not at all confident

(Q25) Have you ever applied some other open license to your creations? (Select all that apply)

- No
- I can't remember
- GNU General Public License or other GNU license (software)
- Open Data Commons licenses (data)
- other (please specify) [text box]

(Q26) Part 3: Motivations and Barriers

This section contains questions designed to understand your motivations for and barriers to using Creative Commons licenses to openly license your language-related digital creations.

(Q27) Have you ever been motivated to apply a Creative Commons license to your own creations in order to do any of the following activities? (Select all that apply)

- To participate in the Wikimedia ecosystem (Wikipedia, Wikimedia, Wikidata, etc.).
- To participate in a competition (e.g., a photography or short story competition).
- To submit an application for a grant, scholarship, fellowship.
- To promote open access.
- To promote open knowledge.
- To participate in the open movement.
- To promote equity of access to digital media content.
- Other (please specify) [text box]

(Q28) Have you ever considered applying a CC license to your own creation, but then decided not to?

- yes, next Q
- maybe, next Q
- no, skip to Q30

(Q29) What prevented you from applying a CCL to your creation? (Select all that apply)

- I did not know which CCL to use.
- I could not decide which CCL to use.
- I could not find information that explained the licenses.
- I did not understand copyright well enough to apply/pick a CC license.
- I did not understand that CC licenses work in conjunction with copyright.
- I did not think that a creation needs to be licensed since I can just share it however I want.
- If I can't make any money off my creation, I don't want anyone else to either.
- I decided that I did not want to share my creation.
- I did not want other people to be able to share my creation.
- I did not want other people to be able to adapt or remix my creation.
- I did not want someone from outside my culture to share/adapt/remix my creation about my culture/language.

- I decided that it was not appropriate to claim copyright ownership over traditional cultural expressions or knowledge.
- The copyright is not mine to claim, so I cannot license the creation.
- I was not sure if the content of my creation qualifies for copyright protection or not.
- The content of my creation (e.g., ethnobotanical terms) probably did not qualify for copyright protection; therefore, I cannot license it.
- Other (please specify) [text box]

(Q30) Do you think that Creative Commons licenses are appropriate ways to license your language-related digital creations?

- Definitely yes
- Probably yes
- Neutral
- Probably not
- Definitely not

(Q31*) Why or why not?

- [text box]

(Q32) Think about the **content** (not the format) of your language-related creations. Here are some examples, but please think about your own materials: **[bullet list of examples:]** videos to teach language use, videos of oral histories from an Origin community, videos demonstrating cultural practices, picture and word books to teach vocabulary, blog posts about community-related topics, academic journal articles, ethnobotanical databases, dictionary databases. **[end bullet list of examples]**.

Of the digital media that you create, would it be appropriate to apply Creative Commons licenses to any of these materials based on their content (not their format)?

- CC licenses are appropriate for the content of **ALL** of my creations.
- CC licenses are appropriate for the content of **SOME** of my creations.
- CC licenses are appropriate for the content of **NONE** of my creations.

(Q33*) Please explain.

- [text box]

(Q34) Part 4: Using CC-licensed creations

This section will ask you questions about how you use and interact with CC-licensed creations that were created by other people. Please read the following definition before answering the questions in this section. This definition is available [here](#) (link opens in a new tab) for easier access as you answer the questions in this section.

- *Adaptation, remix, derivative work*: a creation that is based on another work or on multiple other works. In the Creative Commons ecosystem, the terms *adaptation*, *remix*, and *derivative work* are used interchangeably.

(Q35) Have you ever shared CC-licensed creations that were created by other people? For example, have you shared them via any of the digital sharing platforms listed in Part 1? (To see this list again, click [here](#); the link will open in a new tab.)

- yes
- maybe
- no

(Q36) Have you ever adapted/remixed/reused CC-licensed creations to make a new creation?

- yes, next Q
- maybe, next Q
- no, skip to Q39

(Q37) Did you apply a CC license to your resulting adaptation/remix/derivative creation(s)?

- yes, next Q
- maybe, next Q
- no, skip to Q 39

(Q38) Which CC license did you apply to your adaptation/remix/derivative creation(s)?

- 6 CC license buttons
- CC0 button
- I can't remember

(Q39) How confident do you feel about your understanding of how to *share* CC-licensed creations that were created by other people?

- Very confident
- Somewhat confident
- Neutral
- Somewhat unconfident
- Not at all confident

(Q40) How confident do you feel about your understanding of how to *adapt/reuse/remix* CC-licensed creations that were created by other people?

- Very confident
- Somewhat confident
- Neutral
- Somewhat unconfident
- Not at all confident

(Q41) How confident do you feel in your understanding of how to *apply a CC license to an adaptation/remix/derivative work* that you created using other CC-licensed creations?

- Very confident
- Somewhat confident
- Neutral
- Somewhat unconfident

- Not at all confident

(Q42) For which of the following purposes would you be interested in adapting/reusing/remixing CC-licensed creations? (Select all that apply)

- To get new ideas and inspiration or to spark creativity.
- To supplement my existing language-related creations to help facilitate my work.
- To make them relevant to or useable by Origin community members, collaborators, team members, language learners, or other people (e.g., translating a creation into a different language, etc.).
- To recreate the concept of the creation, but in a context that is relevant to my work/community.
- I have no interest in using/reusing/remixing/adapting CC-licensed creations.
- other (please specify) [text box]

(Q 43) Which of the following do you see as barriers (for you or your collaborators) to using/reusing/remixing/adapting/sharing CC-licensed creations? (Select all that apply)

- Not knowing where/how to find CC-licensed creations.
- Not having time to search for CC-licensed creations that are relevant to my specific context (work, culture, language, Origin Community, etc.).
- Difficulty finding CC-licensed creations that are relevant to my specific context (work, culture, language, Origin Community, etc.).
- Difficulty changing or editing CC-licensed creations.
- Not knowing if I have permission to modify the CC-licensed creations.
- Not knowing if I am allowed to sell my adaptation/remix/derivative of a CC-licensed creation.
- Difficulty integrating CC-licensed creations into the technology I use.
- Not enough time to experiment with adapting/remixing/reusing CC-licensed creations.
- Lack of connections with other people who adapt/remix/reuse CC-licensed creations.
- Difficulty getting collaborators to accept the practice of adapting CC-licensed creations.
- Other (please specify) [text box]

Thank You

Your time is a valuable gift. Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey.

If you have follow-up questions, please contact the Principal Investigator at **[add name and email]**.

If you would like to learn more about Creative Commons licenses, the [Creative Commons Certificate Course](#) is an excellent resource to learn more about the licenses, as well as their use and the open knowledge community which supports them.

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[End of Survey in Qualtrics]

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